

DAMAGE RESISTANCE OF THREE-DIMENSIONALLY WOVEN CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This experimental work compares the damage resistance performance of a 3D woven composite to that of a conventional multi-directional laminate of comparable thickness, stiffness, and strength. Both materials were manufactured from Hexcel[®] IM7 carbon fibers and Cycom[®] PR520 toughened epoxy matrix using the resin transfer molding technique.

Damage resistance was evaluated using standard low-velocity drop-weight impact testing (AITM 1-0010 with minor adaptations) under Barely Visible Impact Damage (BVID)-type conditions. Tests were performed with impact energies ranging from 20 to 130 J using a 16 mm hemispherical tup. Resulting damage was assessed using energy absorption analysis, damage area measurement with ultrasonic through-transmission C-scan imaging, failure mode analysis using micro-computed tomography (μ CT), and simple dent depth measurements.

Comparisons were made between the responses of the two material systems by presenting the energy absorption, dent depth and C-scan damage-area metrics as functions of incident impact energy. This approach yielded a comprehensive understanding of the damage containment properties of the 3D woven composite. Additional insights into damage mechanisms were obtained using μ CT scanning.

The 3D woven composite was found to absorb greater energy per unit damage area, lesser total energy for impacts over 50 J, and to suffer less damage by the metrics of C-scan area and dent depth.

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the most critical limitations of conventional laminated carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP) is their susceptibility to delamination. In the case of low-velocity impact, this failure mode presents the potential for critical strength and stiffness reduction without commensurate visual indication of damage [1],[2]. In light of this unique response, the design and certification of CFRP primary aircraft structures has required that new methodology be developed. Regulatory agencies such as the U.S. Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) and European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) have published guidance [3],[4] indicating that load-carrying requirements should be directly dependent on damage detectability. Namely, undetectable damage is required to be ultimate-load capable for the structure's lifetime [3]–[5].

The most commonly used design methodology involves the development of zone-dependent impact threat assessments based on in-service damage records, threshold of detectability studies linked to in-service inspection methods [6]–[7], and material damage resistance and tolerance characterization.

Material damage resistance characterization describes the relationships between incident impact parameters and damage detectability metrics: for example, the dent depth or C-scan damage area as a function of incident impact energy levels. Damage tolerance characterization describes the relationships between damage detectability metrics and post-damage structural performance: for example, the compression-after-impact strength or fatigue life as a function of damage area.

With these tools, primary structure designs can be produced which ensure against failure with the same or greater confidence as the equivalent metallic structure, all the while utilizing the improved fatigue and corrosion properties of CFRP to significantly increase inspection intervals and decrease scheduled maintenance burdens [8]–[9]. Nevertheless, accidental damage and delamination are still of concern, particularly due to ground handling and maintenance [11]. The next generation of composite materials are being developed which eliminate the delamination failure mode and offer enhanced through-the-thickness performance using three-dimensional pre-formed fiber architectures [11]–[12]. The use of 3D woven composites may have the potential to further reduce life cycle cost of aircraft structures by reducing the probability of detectable damage and associated unscheduled maintenance occurrence.

2 MATERIAL DESCRIPTION AND SPECIFICATIONS

2.1 Description of materials

Both materials evaluated were manufactured by Albany Engineered Composites, Inc. (AEC) using the resin transfer molding technique. Constituent materials for both composites were Hexcel® IM7 carbon fibers and Cycom® PR520 toughened epoxy matrix. The 3D woven composite was a ply-to-ply architecture with a warp tow spacing of 2.54 mm. The designed warp/weft reinforcement ratio — 60% warp, 40% weft — resulted in a warp/pick tow spacing of 4.14 mm and nominal thickness of 4.42mm. 24k tows were used throughout. No straight “stuffer” tows were included in this architecture. All warp and weft tows also acted as through-thickness binders.

The 2D baseline material was a 24-layer multidirectional symmetric non-crimp fabric (NCF) laminate. The laminate schedule [-45/+45/0/90/0/+45/-45/0/0/0/90/45]s was chosen by AEC as a typical layup (44/44/11) used by aerospace OEMs for aircraft applications. The approximate reinforcement distribution was 42% in the 0°, 42% in the ±45°, and 17% in the 90° directions. Similar reinforcement distributions have been used in fiber-dominated layups for fighter aircraft [7], [14]. Nominal thickness was 4.42 mm. Individual NCF laminae were comprised of unidirectional 12k carbon tows weighing 194 g/m². A polyester stitch thread was used running perpendicular to the tows with a spacing of 2 mm and a total weight of 9.15 g/m².

2.2 Mechanical Properties

Both materials were evaluated with standard acid digestion [15], tensile [16], compressive [17], and v-notch shear [18] experiments. The average fiber-volume fraction (ASTM D3171-15 Method 1 Proc. B) for the 3D ply-to-ply (24k/24K) material was 58.4% with standard deviation 1.06%, and for the NCF (12K) material was 57.2% with standard deviation 0.56%. Experimental tensile, compressive, and shear properties are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Experimental mechanical properties

Material/ Orientation	Ultimate Strength			Modulus		
	MPa (CV)			GPa (CV)		
	Tension (ASTM D3039)	Compression (ASTM D6641)	Shear (ASTM D7078)	Tension (ASTM D3039)	Compression (ASTM D6641)	Shear (ASTM D7078)
3D/Warp	1120 (8.00%)	399 (10.2%)	115 (0.81%)	85.8 (4.51%)	75.5 (5.04%)	5.31 (4.41%)
3D/Bias	176 (2.92%)	181 (2.14%)	--	17.5 (5.52%)	16.7 (4.22%)	--
3D/Weft	393 (7.54%)	239 (6.87%)	--	43.5 (3.69%)	41.9 (6.38%)	--
2D/0°	983 (1.96%)	328 (9.13%)	258 (4.20%)	72.2 (3.76%)	64.0 (2.03%)	18.3 (0.98%)
2D/45°	709 (5.21%)	308 (10.2%)	--	51.8 (1.87%)	46.9 (7.19%)	--
2D/90°	566 (6.37%)	293 (7.79%)	--	40.7 (2.76%)	38.8 (4.09%)	--

3 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

3.1 Drop-weight impact testing

Drop-weight impact testing was carried out using Airbus Industries AITM 1-0010 [19] as the primary reference. The airbus standard was chosen over ASTM D7136 [20] since the compression-after-impact fixture design allows for more accurate application of boundary conditions [21], which is an important consideration of the partner study to this research which investigates damage tolerance performance [22].

A Ceast Fractovis Plus (9350 series) drop tower was used to perform the testing. Figure 1a shows the drop tower apparatus with a test specimen in place on the support fixture. Figure 1b shows the important support fixture dimensions in mm [inches], including the standard AITM 1-0010 test specimen, which is shaded. Specimens were clamped lightly with four neoprene-tipped toggle clamps to prevent the specimen from rebounding. As indicated, clamp tips were positioned inside the cut-out of the support fixture so as not to influence specimen response during the impact event.

Figure 1: Impact test setup showing (a) Ceast Fractovis Plus drop-weight apparatus and (b) Dimensions of specimen and specimen support fixture

A 16-mm hemispherical striker was used with an embedded 40-kN load cell. A Ceast DAS64K high-speed data acquisition system was used to obtain real-time contact force data from the load cell during impact. Data was recorded at 4000 kHz. Given the total falling mass — striker, carriage, and additional weights — CEASTVIEW software used numerical integrations of the contact force history to obtain velocity, position, and absorbed energy histories. This integration scheme has been used historically and calculation details are presented in [23].

Kinetic energy of the striker was stored by the test specimen primarily as elastic strain energy and released as fracture surface energy. Additional minor losses were incurred through acoustic emission and plastic deformation. The difference between the peak energy storage and the final energy storage, or energy absorption, represents the elastic strain energy used to rebound the striker. Figure 2 shows the stored energy plots for 30, 60, and 90 Joule impact tests.

Figure 2: Stored energy vs. time for 30, 60, and 90 J strikes

Single specimens from both material systems were subjected to impacts at 20, 25, 40, 50, 60, 70, 90, 110, and 130 J. Three specimens from each material system were subjected to 30-J impacts. Falling mass was adjusted to comply with the drop height (> 0.5 m) requirement set in AITM 1-0010, as well as regulating impact velocity, which was maintained between 3.0 and 4.25 m/s for this study.

Immediately following impact, maximum dent depth was measured to within 0.05 mm using a digital depth micrometer. Maximum dent depth was referenced to four datum points located 20 mm from point of impact along each principal material axis. Because of the delayed nature of aircraft inspections, post-impact material relaxation must be accounted for [1]. Test specimens were allowed to rest for 16 days in the standard environment (70°F, 50% RH), during which time average dent depths decreased on average by 6% for the 2D material and 11% for the 3D material.

3.2 Ultrasonic C-scan

Specimens were ultrasonically tested using a JSR Ultrasonics DPR300 pulser-receiver with two 0.75 inch, 5.0 MHz transducers in through-transmission mode. The couplant used was deionized water (immersion scan) with a total path-length of 6 inches. Pulse amplitude was 527 Volts using 59 Ohms damping. Pulse repetition frequency was 100 Hz, and receiver filter passband was set between 1.0 and 15 MHz.

A preliminary gain study was carried out on one 3D and one 2D impacted specimen to determine an appropriate receiver gain for the remaining trials. The gains tested varied between 6 and 20 dB in 2 dB increments. Detected damage area was not found to vary significantly with gain over this range. It was noted that higher gain levels tended to produce images with a wider range of grayscale values which increased resolution and ease of visual differentiation between damaged and non-damaged regions. For this reason, maximum gains were chosen with the constraint that no saturation (white pixels) occurred. These criteria resulted in a receiver gain level of 9 dB for the 2D baseline specimens and 8 dB for the 3D woven specimens.

During trials, C-scan damage area was measured using three techniques, here referred to as “ASTM ray”, “arbitrary polygon” and “pixel counting”. The ASTM ray technique is presented in ASTM D7136 [20] and involves placing rays radially outward from the center of damage at each 30 degrees. A polygon is inscribed between the intersections of each ray and the damage boundary. The damage area is approximated as the area of the inscribed polygon. In practice, it was found that irregular damage geometries such as those occurring in the delaminations of the 2D baseline material were not accurately approximated and large areas might go uncounted. This issue persisted even with more closely (15 degrees) spaced rays, as illustrated in Figure 3a. Figure 3b shows the arbitrary polygon method, where a user manually selected points which create a border around the visible damage.

Figure 3: C-scan damage area measurement: (a) Deficiency of 'ASTM ray' method illustrated on 50-J 2D specimen with irregular damage shape, and (b) Arbitrary polygon area selection method

The pixel counting method was undertaken in an attempt to automate damage area measurement. This task was a two-step process utilizing an automatic thresholding algorithm to assign pixels below threshold intensity (low signal reception) to black. Continuous regions of these low intensity pixels were then automatically selected and counted. To obtain the damage area in mm^2 , the ratio of counted damage pixels to total pixels was multiplied by the known specimen area.

Five automatic thresholding algorithms were tested: four of them using implementations available in the Fiji distribution of Image-J [24], a popular open-source image-processing program; Huang Fuzziness, Maximum Entropy, Li Minimum Cross Entropy, and Histogram Mean. Citation to the algorithms are provided in the Image-J documentation available online [25]. One additional histogram-based technique was implemented using 3D Composite Studio (3DCS™) Verifier™, which is an image analysis software developed by AEC. All thresholding methods were found to reasonably approximate the visible damage boundary, with the exception of the Huang Fuzziness method, which significantly under-represented the damage region in this application.

Three area selection algorithms were tested: two of them using Image-J ('Wand' and 'Lasso and Blow' tools), and one using 3DCS™ Verifier™. These tools proved effective on simple geometries but failed to accurately capture complex or discontinuous damage regions. Additionally, following an example by Wronkowicz et al. [26] it was desired to count inclusions of non-damaged or apparently non-damaged material within the damaged region, which was not accomplished using these tools. For this study, the arbitrary polygon technique was selected to report C-scan damage areas since it did not suffer the shortcomings of the other two methods.

3.3 Micro-computed tomography

μCT scans were conducted using a resolution of $83 \mu\text{m}$. 3DCS™ Verifier™ was used to perform analysis. Damage profiles are presented and were analyzed using cross-sectional views oriented normal to the warp (0-degree), and weft (90-degree) directions and centered in the specimen.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Damage resistance was characterized by the measurement of dent depth, C-scan damage area, peak force, and absorbed energy. The net performance differences between the two materials varied with impact energy. Specifically, the 2D NCF material exhibited a bilinear response for both dent depth and C-scan damage area relative to impact energy. The slope of the dent depth vs. impact energy response increased sharply at 40 J, while damage area slope decreased moderately at 65 J. The 3D woven material exhibited linear responses for both metrics to high energy levels.

This discussion section will explain these behaviors, drawing on the evidence of impact force histories, ultrasonic C-scans, and μ CT images particularly at the 30 J and 90 J impact energy levels. Summary plots of the damage resistance metrics relative to incident energy are also presented.

4.1 Impact force and absorbed energy

In the range 0–50 J, the 2D NCF and 3D woven composites displayed similar force-displacement and kinetic energy storage behavior. The 3D woven composite was slightly more compliant, achieving lower peak force but higher maximum deflection. No significant failures occurred beyond matrix cracking, which is evident by the irregular noise pattern of plate vibration in Figure 4, which shows the force-time and force-displacement curves for 30 J impacts.

Figure 4: Force histories for 30-J impact tests: (a) Force vs. time and (b) Force vs. displacement

For impacts of 50 J and higher, contact force on the 2D NCF material reached about 14kN peak. 14kN proved to be an incipient force for failure, where significant force drop occurred. Contact force for the remainder of the impact event remained fairly constant in the neighborhood of 9–11 kN until striker velocity decreased to zero (peak deflection.) 3D woven specimens experienced earlier failures between 9 and 13 kN. The contact force after first failure was subsequently regained and exceeded as additional load paths were activated within the material.

First failure for both materials was observed to correspond with breaching of the back face. In the case of the 2D NCF, the failure mode was de-bonding of the back-face 45-degree surface tows, which correspond to the diagonal protrusions seen in the ultrasonic C-scans shown in Figure 3 and later in section 4.2. In the case of the 3D woven composite, the woven architecture necessitated not only the debonding of the woven monolith, but also the rupture of tows, which explains the repeating high loads after first failure. When a given tow ruptured, the load redistributed to neighboring tows, which also loaded to failure.

These behaviors are evident in the force-time histories beginning at 50 J, however they are more obvious at higher energy levels where a relatively long period of continuous material failure occurred. Figure 5 shows impact plots for 90-J tests, plainly illustrating the steady force plateau corresponding to the progressive delamination of the 2D NCF back-face surface tows, as well as the oscillating force caused by the successive failure of tows in the 3D woven composite.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: Force histories for 90-J impact tests: (a) Force vs. time and (b) Force vs. displacement

Through increasing energy levels, the 2D NCF specimens accumulated more damage and became more compliant, lengthening the impulse required to stop the striker. There was an inversion of trend at 65 J whereby the normally stiffer 2D NCF composite achieved lower peak force and greater impact duration relative to the 3D composite.

Figure 6a shows the absorbed energy by both material systems for all¹ tests, plotted relative to the initial impactor kinetic energies, such that the line $y = x$ represents complete energy absorption i.e., no striker rebound. The differences were minimal up to 50 J, where significant failures were observed. In the range 50–110 J, the 3D woven material stored and reflected a greater proportion of energy as elastic strain instead of damage creation. At 130 J, both materials were fully perforated. In the case of perforation, the striker carried kinetic energy through the plate as it passed. Because energy absorption was calculated based on the integration of force history, the actual absorbed energy could not be calculated and was taken as 100% of incident.

Although total energy absorbed has been a typical measure of impact resistance, Kuboki et al [27] reported no change in total absorbed energy between impact specimens of greatly varying fracture toughness. The authors suggested an alternative metric for impact resistance, namely absorbed energy per unit damage area. This metric is presented for the present study in Figure 6b. Although measurement noise and material scatter are present, linear trends are clearly visible in the range 50-110 J. The 3D woven composite exhibited a steady improvement over the range when compared to the 2D NCF using this metric, owing to the mechanical energy dissipation mode of tow breakage as opposed to delamination.

¹ 40-Joule 2D NCF impact not recorded due to data acquisition malfunction.

Figure 6: Absorbed energy summary: (a) Total absorbed energy and (b) Absorbed energy per unit C-scan damage area

4.2 Ultrasonic C-scan and dent depth damage analysis

As was previously noted, the 2D NCF exhibited two distinct modes of delamination growth. At low energies, back-face damage was minor, and projected delamination area extended outward radially in a round, to elliptical, to diamond-shaped profile as seen in Figure 7 a-b. The second phase of delamination growth occurred beyond the 50-J energy level where critical load for back-face delamination was first achieved. As seen in Figure 7 c-d, delamination growth between 50 J and 130 J was primarily accumulated by the widening and lengthening of this debonded back-face region, while the area of the diamond-shape core delamination region increased only marginally.

Damage area in the 3D woven material increased quasi-linearly to 90 J, then decreased markedly up to perforation energy. Figures 8a-d show the progression of damage outcomes in the 3D woven composite with increasing energy strikes.

Figure 7 : Progression of damage outcomes in the 2D NCF composite with increasing energy strikes: (a) 20 J, (b) 50 J, (c) 90 J, and (d) 130 J

Figure 8 : Progression of damage outcomes in 3D woven composite with increasing energy strikes: (a) 20 J, (b) 50 J, (c) 90 J, and (d) 130 J

The 3D woven composite outperformed the 2D NCF composite in the containment of damage. Figure 9a shows the total projected damage area plotted as a function of incident impact energy. The bi-linear response of the 2D NCF clearly summarizes the dual energy absorption modes. The same phenomenon had a significant effect on the permanent dent depth. Figure 9b shows the permanent dent depth in its relaxed state for both materials. The 2D NCF exhibits a sharp knee at 40 J, 50 J being the first energy level with significant back-face delamination. The 3D composite presented a much tougher barrier to striker dent depth at energy levels greater than 40 J, increasing quasi-linearly with energy over the investigated energy range.

Figure 9: Progression of damage outcomes with impact energy: (a) C-scan damage area and (b) permanent dent depth

4.3 Microcomputed tomography damage analysis

In the low-energy range 0–30 J, the 2D NCF and 3D woven composites displayed similar load-displacement and kinetic energy storage behavior, as well as incurring similar damage area and permanent dent depth. Despite these similarities, the progression of damage outcomes in the two materials were distinctly different. The 2D material exhibited diagonal through-thickness matrix cracking accompanied by significant delaminations, which occurred primarily at interfaces of 90-degree orientation separation. The delaminations were roughly peanut-shaped and aligned with the tows of the lower ply. These observations match the expectations for low velocity impact of composite laminates from Abrate [28] and experimental observations in the literature [29], [30]. Figure 10 shows the 0-degree section of a 2D specimen impacted at 30 J. Matrix cracking and delaminations at the interfaces between plies 4 and 5, and plies 14 and 15 were observed on the 0-degree section for all three specimens.

Figure 10: μ CT image of 2D NCF specimen impacted at 30 J (0 degree view)

The 3D woven specimens impacted at 30 J exhibited diagonal shear cracking when viewed in both the warp and weft planes, suggesting roughly conical damage morphology as is typical in the case of impact on thick, brittle plates [28], [31]–[32]. Figure 11 shows a warp cross-section located between weft tows. This cross-section is about 2 mm off-center in the specimen, since the impact was not targeted with respect to the unit cell. At this cross-section, the conical shear cracks progress freely, splitting impregnated warp tows and neat resin pockets.

Figure 11: μ CT image of 3D ply to ply specimen impacted at 30 J (warp view, between weft tows)

Examining a warp section within a stack of weft tows (Figure 12), no shear cracks were observed, since cracks at this orientation would necessarily sever the weft tows. A similar pattern, i.e. shear cracking occurring between stacks of tows, was observed in the weft section, and was observed for all 30-J, 3D specimens.

Figure 12: μ CT image of 3D ply-to-ply specimen impacted at 30 J (warp view, weft tows visible)

As discussed in section 4.1, successive tow failure was a primary energy absorption mechanism of the 3D woven composite. Figure 12 demonstrates that tow breakage did not occur at low energy. μ CT analysis and impact force histories revealed weft tow breakage at energy levels 50 J and higher.

Figures 13 and 14 clearly illustrate the 3D woven composite's mechanics of impact energy dissipation. Warp tows were firmly rooted in the far field of the specimen and span a long unsupported length due to the AITM 1-0010 or ASTM D7136 asymmetric fixture geometry. During impact, the warp tows straightened and elongated under a tensile-dominated load causing them to progressively de-bond from the surrounding matrix near the impact zone. The 3D ply-to-ply 60/40 reinforcement ratio denotes greater density of warp than weft tows. Since there were fewer weft tows and they were loaded over a shorter unsupported span, they encountered high shear forces and were more easily broken.

With increasing impact energy, additional rows of weft tows were broken. In the case of the 110-Joule 3D impact specimen, which was the highest energy level before perforation occurred, 12 rows of weft tows were ruptured along the specimen centerline. A μ CT image from the 90-J impact specimen, (Figure 13), indicates that all weft tows through the thickness are broken.

Figure 13: 3D woven specimen impacted at 90 J: warp section showing shear cracks and weft tow breakage

Figure 14: 3D woven specimen impacted at 90 J: weft section showing longitudinal cracking/warp tow debonding

5 CONCLUDING REMARKS

The 3D woven composite exhibited greater damage resistance over the entire experimental range when compared with the baseline 2D laminated composite using metrics of in-plane damage containment, dent depth, and energy absorption per unit damage area. In the energy range of 50–110 J, the 3D composite absorbed lower total energy.

These benefits were achieved by virtue of the through-thickness reinforcement which prevented delamination. Additionally, the woven architecture provided a greater resistance to energy absorption by allowing impact loads to be carried by tows, both before and after the initial failure.

The threshold for detectability (BVID) has been taken in industry as a critical dent depth which is likely to be spotted during a general visual inspection (GVI); a well-established maintenance routine in the airline industry. The BVID threshold is between 0.5 mm and 1.3 mm depending on manufacturer [5]–[8]. If the BVID threshold is taken as 1 mm, as in the AITM 1-0010 test standard [19], The energy required to generate BVID was significantly increased from 48 J to 77 J by the use of a 3D-woven composite. If the BVID threshold is taken as 1.3 mm, the increase in required energy was even greater; from 48 J to 100 J. Consequently, the use of 3D woven composites in select applications may reduce the likelihood of detectable damage and non-routine maintenance occurrence. Additionally, C-scan damage area corresponds inversely with residual strength [6] suggesting that 3D woven composites may exhibit better load carrying capacity after impact which could have implications for allowable damage limits and inspection intervals. The results of the damage tolerance experiments will be presented in a future study [22].

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